

Popular Article

Drug Safety Matters: Pharmacovigilance- Concept and Future

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Abstract

Medicines and vaccines are of utmost importance as they form core of nation healthcare system. Deadly incidents in the past like thalidomide tragedy in 1950, use of lash lure mascara, ethylene glycol poisoning in the children necessitated and high lightened the importance of safety of medicines and vaccines. Branch dealing with safety of drugs is known as pharmacovigilance and is a rigorous process throughout the life cycle of drug. Intrinsic limitation up to phase III of drug discovery process, strongly emphasizes the necessity of pharmacovigilance. Present article tries to highlight key aspect of safety process during drug development and its future, and will help drug prescribers and users to a certain extent about efficacious and safe use of drugs in day-to-day life.

Introduction

Medicines and vaccines are the core of healthcare system and have transformed our lives by prevention and treatment of diseases. In addition to their benefits, medicinal products may also have side effects, some of which may be undesirable and / or unexpected (Who.int). Medicines safety is of utmost importance and its monitoring is a continuous and dynamic process throughout all the phases of the life cycle of a drug (Trifirò and Crisafulli, 2022). Deadly incidents in the past like thalidomide tragedy in 1950, use of lash lure mascara, ethylene glycol poisoning in the children due to Elixir Sulphanilamide paved the way for assessment of safety of chemical before their direct authorization for use (National Research Council (US) Committee, 2004). The branch dealing with this matter is known as “pharmacovigilance”. Pharmacovigilance is the science and activities relating to the detection, assessment, understanding and prevention of adverse effects or any other medicine/vaccine related problem (Who.int). Interindividual variations accounting for variation in drug response and to the adverse effect, makes this science interesting, as when it comes to global pharmacovigilance, there is rarely a one-size-fits-all. Overall safety matters related to the drug are therefore assessed at various phases of drug development process.

The overall drug development process occurs in five different stages viz., discovery and development, preclinical research, clinical research, regulatory authority reviews, and finally post marketing safety studies (FDA, 2018). Although, all medicines and vaccines undergo rigorous testing for safety and efficacy through clinical trials before they are authorized for use, these trials were conducted in a relatively small number of selected individuals for a short period of time (Who.int). So, a true picture of drug including its side effects is evident only when these products were used by a heterogenous population, including people with other concurrent diseases, and over a long period of time. This article therefore tries to highlight key aspect of safety process followed during drug development and its future, and will help to drug prescribers and users to a certain extent about efficacious and safe use of drugs in day-to-day life.

Safety Evaluation of Drug in Drug Development Process

After target identification and validation, the drug safety was assessed in pre-clinical studies, where the primary goal of safety evaluation is the identification of a safe dose safety parameters in humans for clinical monitoring (Trifirò and Crisafulli, 2022). In line with this, recently in May, 2022 FDA has made a new initiative termed “Project Optimus” instead of earlier maximum tolerated dose approach employed for cytotoxic chemotherapeutics in order to highlight the importance of characterizing the dose and schedule of the anti-cancer drugs, to maximize efficacy and safety (FDA, 2022). Preclinical safety studies were done using two different animal species, with animals receiving maximum tolerated dose (MTD) of the new drug for 30 or 90 days (National Research Council (US) Committee, 2004). Careful assessment of animals was then done throughout the study to check any side effects. After the study period, toxicity potential of drug was then assessed by conducting post mortem examination if any. All these procedures were carried out as per guidelines laid by FDA or various regulatory authorities.

After finalizing dose drug enters into the clinical phase, consisting of four phases. Phase I studies are carried out in healthy human volunteers to estimate the tolerability of the dose range expected to be needed for later clinical studies. Phase II studies are done in patients with a disease or condition of interest to find suitable dose range. Phase III clinical trials are large multicenter trials involving number of patients with an emphasis on assessment of drug's effectiveness and to continue to monitor for any side effects. Till phase III, drug remains in the premarket phase and despite very rigorous and thorough nature of safely evaluation process, pre-marketing clinical trials will not be in position to extensively evaluate drug safety profile due to intrinsic limitations involving limited number of subjects, confounding the overall results of the study (Trifirò and Crisafulli, 2022).

The next penultimate phase is phase IV (post-marketing surveillance), wherein drug actually enters in the market. In this phase rigorous and exhaustive safety evaluation of drug profile is possible due to exposure of drug to a heterogenous population. This safety profile was analyzed by drug maker and by FDA for the presence of side effects which are likely to arise on account of interindividual variation in the population (National Research Council (US) Committee, 2004). Conclusively phase IV of trial plays an important role for better defining drugs' safety profile in real-world setting, which helps to further strengthen results of pre-

marketing studies, thereby filling the evidence gap.

Importance of Pharmacovigilance

Thalidomide tragedy in 1950, use of lash lure mascara, ethylene glycol poisoning in the children due to Elixir sulphanimide created a need for assessment of safety of chemical before their direct authorization for use (National Research Council (US) Committee, 2004). Despite this, in the last two year, with first wave of COVID-19 pandemic further highlights the importance of pharmacovigilance wherein absence of vaccines and drugs for treatment/prevention of COVID-19, lead to repurposing of several drugs. Various drugs like hydroxychloroquine, ivermectin and azithromycin has been off-label used for the treatment of COVID-19 patients, in the absence of scientific evidence (Sultana et al., 2020a). Risk associated with off label use of these drugs are the important step for pharmacovigilance monitoring. Elucidating further, azithromycin, a macrolide antibiotic that has been widely used, for the treatment of COVID-19 patients despite its proarrhythmogenic activity, led regulatory agencies to issue warnings against the use of this drug, unless in case of bacterial superinfection occurrence (Crisafulli et al., 2021). Global health emergencies like pandemic COVID-19 accelerated the process of drug approval, and of safety evaluation in post-marketing setting with an emphasis on patient safety. Besides this, role of communication between health care providers and patients in relation to appropriate use of medicines/vaccines, further supports and validate the role of pharmacovigilance as number of studies has reported accelerated inappropriate drug use associated with the risk of serious adverse reactions, the best example being the hydroxychloroquine (Sultana et al., 2020b).

Pharmacovigilance-Conclusion and Future Directions

Pharmacovigilance has played crucial role in the safety of medicines all of which at certain extent possess some risk. It has grown in the pharmaceutical industry as well as is recognized as a discipline. With emphasis on reporting of individual cases in the past (Talbot and Nilsson, 1998), we must be ready for the current and future challenges as far as safety and drug regulations are concerned. Medicinal side effects or associated risk can be minimized by the use of good quality, and efficacious medicines. Besides this, rational use of medicines, enhancing communication between the health professionals and the public and educate health professionals to understand the effectiveness or risk of medicines that they prescribe are important steps to take into account (Jeetu and Anusha, 2010). More stringent measures during drug development process and proper risk communication throughout the drug chain since its production to its ultimate use are necessary steps to undertake. In addition, consideration must be given to newer techniques like artificial intelligence, machine learning, use of digital therapeutics and creation of electronic healthcare data ((Trifirò and Crisafulli, 2022). This will offer opportunity for optimizing drug benefit-risk profile evaluation in real world setting. Advanced therapy medicinal products (European Medicines Agency, 2021) are based on genes, cells or tissue engineering is emerging discipline and encompasses personalized or precision medicine also warrant need for post marketing surveillance. In addition to drugs, other biologicals like vaccines may require special pharmacovigilance monitoring in recent years. Lastly, important consideration must be given to adverse effect occurring to nature on account of presence of pharmaceuticals in the environment, although a separate branch

called as “Eco pharmacovigilance” (Velo and Moretti, 2010) is dealing with all this aspect and is a very important issue now a days.

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